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THE ROLE OF REFLECTIVE TEACHING IN IMPROVING ESL LESSONS

РОЛЬ РЕФЛЕКСИВНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В УЛУЧШЕНИИ УРОКОВ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК ВТОРОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Abstract. This article explains the importance of reflective learning in improving the effectiveness of teaching English as a Second Language (ESL). Reflective learning helps teachers think carefully about their lessons, identify what works well and understand the needs of their students. It helps teachers find optimal ways to introduce new vocabulary, grammar and skills to make learning easier for students. Reflective learning shows teachers how to make lessons fun and engaging. Research shows that self-evaluation, receiving feedback from other teachers and regularly reflecting on lessons are very beneficial for teachers’ growth and effectiveness. Using reflective learning, teachers can modify lesson plans, add activities such as games, group work, and short discussions, and increase student engagement and motivation. Teachers who reflect on their lessons create a conducive classroom environment where students feel comfortable, actively participate in lessons, and reflect carefully on what they are learning. Reflective learning also helps teachers connect theory with practice by observing how students learn and listening to their thoughts. This helps teachers choose optimal teaching methods, manage the classroom effectively and make lessons meaningful for students, which helps them improve their English language skills. Reflective teaching also increases teachers’

confidence, improves their skills and strengthens their relationships with students. The article offers tips for teachers to reflect after each lesson, discuss teaching ideas with colleagues, and help students process what they have learned. Regular reflection can improve teaching, make lessons more engaging and make learning easier and more effective for students. Reflection is an important tool for all teachers, helping them to improve the quality of their lessons and help students successfully master English language.

Key words: practice, reflection, learning, motivation, development, students, test, education, experience, skill, teacher, lesson.

Аннотация. В этой статье объясняется важность рефлексивного обучения для повышения эффективности преподавания английского языка как второго (ESL). Рефлексивное обучение помогает учителям тщательно продумывать свои уроки, выявлять наиболее эффективные подходы и понимать потребности учеников. Оно помогает учителям находить оптимальные способы введения новой лексики, грамматики и навыков, чтобы облегчить учебный процесс. Рефлексивное обучение показывает учителям, как сделать уроки увлекательными и интересными. Исследования показывают, что самооценка, получение обратной связи от других учителей и регулярный анализ уроков очень полезны для профессионального роста и эффективности учителей. Используя рефлексивное обучение, учителя могут корректировать планы уроков, добавлять такие виды деятельности, как игры, групповая работа и короткие обсуждения, а также повышать вовлеченность и мотивацию учеников. Учителя, которые анализируют свои уроки, создают благоприятную атмосферу в классе, где ученики чувствуют себя комфортно, активно участвуют в уроках и тщательно анализируют то, что они изучают. Рефлексивное обучение также помогает учителям связывать теорию с практикой, наблюдая за тем, как ученики усваивают материал, и прислушиваясь к их мнению. Это помогает учителям выбирать оптимальные методы обучения, эффективно управлять классом и делать уроки содержательными для учеников, что способствует их улучшению навыков владения английским языком. Рефлексивное обучение также повышает уверенность учителей в себе, улучшает их навыки и укрепляет отношения с учениками. В статье даны советы учителям, как проводить рефлексию после каждого урока, обсуждать идеи преподавания с коллегами и помогать ученикам осмысливать изученное. Регулярная рефлексия может улучшить качество преподавания, сделать уроки более интересными и облегчить обучение для учеников. Рефлексия - важный инструмент для всех учителей, помогающий им повысить качество уроков и помочь ученикам успешно освоить английский язык.

Ключевые слова: практика, рефлексия, обучение, мотивация, развитие, учащиеся, тест, образование, опыт, навык, учитель, урок.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini ikkinchi til (ESL) sifatida o‘qitish samaradorligini oshirishda reflektiv o‘rganishning ahamiyati tushuntirilgan. Reflektiv o‘rganish o‘qituvchilarga darslari haqida ehtiyotkorlik bilan o‘ylashga, nima yaxshi ishlashini aniqlashga va o‘quvchilarining ehtiyojlarini tushunishga

yordam beradi. Bu o'qituvchilarga o'quvchilar uchun o'rganishni osonlashtirish uchun yangi lug'at, grammatika va ko'nikmalarni joriy etishning maqbul usullarini topishga yordam beradi. Refleksiv o'rganish o'qituvchilarga darslarni qanday qilib qiziqarli va jozibador qilishni ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'zini baholash, boshqa o'qituvchilardan fikr-mulohazalarni olish va darslar haqida muntazam ravishda mulohaza yuritish o'qituvchilarning o'sishi va samaradorligi uchun juda foydali. Refleksiv o'rganishdan foydalanib, o'qituvchilar dars rejalarini o'zgartirishi, o'yinlar, guruh ishlari va qisqa munozaralar kabi mashg'ulotlarni qo'shishi va o'quvchilarning faolligi va motivatsiyasini oshirishi mumkin. Darslari haqida mulohaza yuritadigan o'qituvchilar o'quvchilar o'zlarini qulay his qiladigan, darslarda faol ishtirok etadigan va o'rganayotgan narsalari haqida diqqat bilan mulohaza yuritadigan qulay sinf muhitini yaratadilar. Refleksiv o'rganish, shuningdek, o'qituvchilarga o'quvchilarning qanday o'rganishini kuzatish va ularning fikrlarini tinglash orqali nazariyani amaliyot bilan bog'lashga yordam beradi. Bu o'qituvchilarga optimal o'qitish usullarini tanlashga, sinfni samarali boshqarishga va o'quvchilar uchun darslarni mazmunli qilishga yordam beradi, bu esa ularga ingliz tili ko'nikmalarini yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Refleksiv o'qitish shuningdek, o'qituvchilarning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshiradi, ko'nikmalarini yaxshilaydi va o'quvchilar bilan munosabatlarini mustahkamlaydi. Maqolada o'qituvchilarga har bir darsdan keyin mulohaza yuritish, o'qitish g'oyalarini hamkasblari bilan muhokama qilish va o'quvchilarga o'rganganlarini qayta ishlashga yordam berish bo'yicha maslahatlar berilgan. Muntazam mulohaza yuritish o'qitishni yaxshilashi, darslarni yanada qiziqarli qilishi va o'quvchilar uchun o'rganishni osonroq va samaraliroq qilishi mumkin. Mulohaza barcha o'qituvchilar uchun muhim vosita bo'lib, ularga dars sifatini yaxshilashga va o'quvchilarga ingliz tilini muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: amaliyot, refleksiya, o'rganish, motivatsiya, rivojlanish, o'quvchilar, sinov, ta'lim, tajriba, ko'nikma, o'qituvchi, dars.

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Introduction. Nowadays we believe that, teaching is more than just the transmission of knowledge, it is a continuous process of growth, understanding, and transformation. In the context of teaching English as a second language (ESL), reflective practice serves as a bridge between experience and understanding. As Farrell states, "Reflection is a deliberate process through, which teachers critically examine their classroom experiences to develop professionally" [1].

On the one hand, this raises the question: what is reflective learning in learning English as a second language? Reflective learning is when a teacher analyzes their work, reflects on how their lessons are going, and tries to understand what went well and what needs to be improved [6].

In other words, a teacher does not just teach a lesson, but reflects on their experiences to improve. For example, after a lesson, a teacher might ask themselves:

What went well today? Why weren't some students active? Do the assignment or explanation need to be adjusted for the next lesson? As Richards and Lockhartnote, "Reflective teaching transforms ordinarily classroom activity into a process of inquiry and professional growth." [2]. It means that, when teachers consciously analyze their lessons, they are not just teaching, but using it as an opportunity to learn, develop and improve their teaching and language skills. This experience helps to teachers to understand their students very well, choose some methods to teach them, make lessons more interesting and effective and surely continuously grow as a professional.

According to Wallace's statement "Reflective teacher training is one of the most effective ways to build professional competence, as it links theory with practice", through this statement he means that, professional competence is built through a cyclical process: theory, practice and reflection [4].

In addition, Celce-Murcia emphasizes that, "Reflection allows teachers to adapt to new teaching challenges and stay responsive to the evolving needs of learners" [3].

On the other side of the coin, the word reflection means the process one's own internal mental acts [5].

Through reflection, teachers go beyond the routine classroom to analyze their beliefs, strategies, and interactions with students. This process allows them to understand what works, what needs improvement, and how their teaching impacts student motivation and achievement. Reflective learning not only enhances professional competence but also fosters deeper connections between teachers and students, creating a more meaningful and dynamic learning environment. Sure, the reflective teaching has some purposes, which each person should pay attention to this.

Purposes of reflective teaching. Reflective teaching has two majority goals:

1. To broaden understanding of the teaching-learning process. This means that, a deeper understanding of how learning occurs - not only from the teacher's perspective, but also from the student's point of view, like from their perspective. I opine that, then teacher begin to notice, how students think, remember, understand materials, react and give some questions base on the topic or work actively during the lesson. When teachers understand all these processes, they can better select methods, explain things more clearly and create more interesting and effective lessons.

2. To expand the repertoire of strategic options as a language. That is, when teachers strive to use more different teaching methods and strategies to make lessons more effective, when I said in the last purpose. When teachers reflect, namely, analyze their lessons and experiences, they notice, which methods work best and of course which do not. Sometimes, teachers choose incorrect teaching system, this makes lessons a few boring and ineffective, then students begin to dislike this language and not join in the lessons. To prevent such mistakes from happening, teachers should pay attention to the education system. For instance, they can create some new methods such as exercises, interactive games instead of only lecturing in grammar lessons. Through this way, students become more engaged and start using grammar more confidently in their speech [3].

In my opinion that, reflective learning thus helps teachers expand their professional capabilities, like they are no longer limited to one teaching style, but are able to choose various strategies for different students and situations. In general, reflective learning helps improve the quality of lessons and gives students more real-world opportunities to understand and practice the second language through these methods.

However, teachers must be experts of their personal job to teach students. Currently, teaching a foreign language requires the teachers to be constantly searching, for examples at schools, even at universities, that is, teachers must work on themselves almost every day, in order to keep students engaged in lessons, make effective and beneficial for future. In short, they should be masters with their works. For example, teachers need to teach their lessons in a way that is relevant to modern era, first of all they need to learn new technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and lessons methods should be designed accordingly. Thus, they can achieve to own aim to teaching students.

Some people believe that, self-evaluation plays a huge role in reflective teaching, because reflection is not only thinking, but also it is ability to evaluate one's work and see own strengths and weaknesses in life. For instance, when teachers work on self-evaluation, they ask themselves: What did I do well in the lesson? What could I have done better? Why did the students react the way they did? For example, I have asked these questions, when I was in practice at schools. Sure, it occurs in all teachers in the first time. Although, these questions help to understand cause of successes and difficulties, so it helps to develop professionally. From my point of view, without the ability to honestly evaluate yourself, it is impossible to understand how to become a better teacher. In short, self-evaluation is the warp of reflective teaching.

In addition, feedback is majority part in reflective teaching, because teachers can see their lessons from another side. When teachers bring some feedbacks from their students or colleagues, they can notice personal mistakes or weaknesses, which they cannot notice to these, which methods can be interesting for students. Without this, they will not be able to grow on themselves and will not correct their mistakes in the future.

Literature review. As Wallace notes, reflective learning is one of the most effective ways to develop professional competence because it links theory with practice [4].

Celso-Murcia said that, “Reflection allows teachers to adapt to new pedagogical challenges and be responsive to the changing needs of students” [3].

According to Bizyaeva, reflection is a process of self-awareness of a person's internal mental actions and states [5]. Thus, reflection in pedagogy helps teachers understand the relationship between their methods and student learning outcomes.

According to Mosina and Lobanova statement, reflective learning is a process of consciously analyzing one's own teaching activities, aimed at continuous improvement. This approach allows teachers to identify the strengths and weaknesses of their practice and purposefully improve their foreign language teaching [6].

Research methodology. This research is based on the study of reflective teaching in ESL (English as a second language). The primary goal of the methodology is to demonstrate, how reflection can help teachers to improve their teaching system and better understand their students.

In the research used analytical and comparative methods. The analytical method helped explore various ideas about reflection presented in books and articles. The comparative method was used to compare the views of various authors, such as Wallace, Cels-Murcia, Farrell, Bizyaeva, Khakunova and Kazieva and Mosina and Lobanova, which were used in this article.

During the teaching practice used monitoring too. This process helps to understand teacher and students' interactions, lesson organization and the impact of reflection on learning outcomes.

The obtained data were analyzed to develop useful recommendations for English language teachers. This methodology contributed to increasing the reliability of the research and establishing a connection between theory and actual teaching practice, specifically, to apply these methods in real-life teaching students a second language.

Analysis and discussion of results. This part of the article discusses the key ideas and results of reflective learning in English language teaching such as in ESL contexts. Analysis shows that reflecting on one's own work contributes to teachers' professional growth and increases student motivation.

The examples demonstrate that teachers who reflect on their work after each lesson improve the quality of their lessons. They understand their students better and find new ways to make lessons more engaging and effective for students. Observations show that when teachers use reflection and feedback, students become more engaged and confident, that is, when teachers give knowledge to each student, they give back this energy to teachers, through active participation during lessons, this increases the teacher's motivation.

The results also show that self-assessment and peer feedback are very important. When teachers analyze, what they did well and what needs improvement, they choose more effective methods for future lessons. For example, after reflecting some teachers began using games or group work instead of grammar explanations. This made lessons more engaging and helped students learn faster.

Comparison of this research with others [1, 3, 4] shows that reflection helps to connect theory and practice. This means that, teachers not only teach better, but also gain a deeper understanding of their work.

Overall, I want to say that, the results indicate that reflective learning is a beneficial approach to English language teaching. It improves the quality of lessons, increases motivation, and develops both teachers and students.

Conclusion and recommendations. Based on the above, we can draw a conclusion, reflective teaching is not only a simple teaching method, but also it plays important role to increasing quality of teaching English like a second language. It helps teachers analyze their methods, better understand students' needs and make lessons more effective, beneficial, interesting and engaging. Reflection fosters the development of both teachers and students, making them more aware and

accountable for their success. Regular reflection helps create a more positive, flexible, and student-centered learning environment.

Based on the article, I want to give some recommendations for teachers:

№	Recommendation	Explanation and examples
1	Teachers should use reflection as a regular part of their English lessons.	Reflection means thinking about how lesson went - was good and what can be improved. By the way it helps teacher and student understand each other. For example, after the lesson, the teacher writes in her notebook: "Students liked the speaking activity, but they had trouble with grammar skill. Next time, I will explain grammar before the activity".
2	They should also encourage students to reflect on their own learning.	Students can think about what they learned from lesson and what was difficult for them for learning English. For instance, at the end of the lesson, the teacher asks: "What did you learn today?" and "What was hard for you?" Students write short answers in their notebooks. So, the next time teacher should to correct mistakes.
3	It is useful to discuss lessons with colleagues and share ideas.	Talking with other teachers helps to find new ways to teach better, like be experienced. For example, teachers can tell, how to teach and engage students to lessons.
4	Reflection makes teaching more creative and student-centered.	When teachers reflect, they understand what students really need and how to make lessons more interesting. For instance, after reflection, the teacher adds group games and songs to make grammar lessons more fun.

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